

PHRASEOLOGIZMS IN TEACHING PROCESS

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Annotation. The purpose of this scientific work is a theoretical analysis of the important aspects of phraseology in the teaching process and its semantics

Key words: semantics, meaning, phraseologizm, idiom, teaching process, linguistic unit.

Part of the vocabulary is an important element of culture, and at the same time, it is a sign of students' free and effective use of a foreign language. English is a highly idiomatic language, and English speakers use idiomatic expressions widely in various fields, including the media, literature, and colloquial speech. In most textbooks of English as a foreign language, it is suggested to study phraseological units such as currency, color, body, food, musical idioms in groups. The method of teaching phraseological units with components turned out to be more effective. Because idioms are "culturally bound" elements of vocabulary that easily fall into specific categories, which at the same time facilitates the learning process. In teaching, vocabulary and syntax or vocabulary (phraseology as a part of vocabulary) and grammar have traditionally been considered as discrete aspects of language [M. Hoey, 2005; U. Romer, 2009.], but many scholars from different theoretical camps of applied linguistics and second language acquisition argue that they are actually inseparable. The importance of phraseological research is always discussed as it shows the relationship between language and society. In speech, phraseological units have connotations associated with emotion and meaning. Connotation is determined only by the social and ideological attitude of the speaker, so the evaluative component of such connotation is subjective. Knowledge of English phraseological units, proverbs and sayings enriches students' vocabulary and helps them understand the figurative system of the English language, expands their linguistic and cultural competence.

The vocabulary of the English language consists of words and word equivalents that are not created by speakers, but are used as ready-made language units. Such units are characterized, first of all, by the conflict between the semantic integrity of the whole and the formal independence of its parts. It is very difficult to establish a clear boundary between free phrases composed by the speaker and phraseological units used in the finished form. The problem of understanding the meaning of a phraseological unit is related to the possibility of diachronically expanding our knowledge of the world. At

the same time, the role of phraseological units as a unique structure in the formation of students' vocabulary and linguistic-cultural competence is very large, because they embody the country's national and cultural outlook. Applied theories of language learning suggest that phraseology should be included in the vocabulary. Phraseology teaching is a part of the foreign teaching methodology and the cultural approach to the organization of vocabulary learning, although the structure of joint meaning is a linguistic approach. Complex methodology is used: method of phraseological identification, semantic analysis.

A phraseological value is a category which is interpreted in different ways depending on understanding of the nature of a phraseological unit, its components and volume of phraseology. According to A.V. Kunin, the phraseological unit is a fixed combination of words which fully or partially change their meanings. (A.V. Kunin, 2005.) It means that a character, which is above the word level, stability and changed meanings of words in the combination are criteria of phraseological units together with other linguistic units, which define their special status in the language structure. "But if we want to characterize the semantic usage properly which is accepted in any speech community and belongs to the described language, we should not only describe it. We can achieve the result only by applying collective estimations which are adopted in the community so we must take into consideration the public opinion. One and the same thing may have different descriptions in different civilizations. Such semantic definitions must have substantial consequences for the formal analysis of linguistic units." [N.N. Zerkina, 2011.] An idea of interrelation between linguistic and extra linguistic meanings in the language and in particular in word semantics is not new. This issue was raised in very general terms in some research works of classical linguists and philosophers and keeps attracting attention of modern scientists. To seek logical arrangements of phraseological units and put them in a more meaningful learning context for foreign language learners, researchers [Kövecses & Szabó 1996] have devoted themselves to looking for certain systematicity in idioms. Likewise, we consider phraseology an interesting issue to focus on because scholars claim that it is a cornerstone within the lexicon of any language. As Mel'cuk (1998:24) states "People speak in set phrases, rather than in separate words in any language" [cited in Fernández Prieto, 2004]. Therefore, knowing a word implies to know the syntagmatic combinations or words that go together with it (be made off money, but for my money). These readymade units are considered extremely difficult by non-native speakers, since they are conventional ways of expression. Nowadays, the teaching of vocabulary has become essential in foreign language teaching and learning, particularly in the latest

years. Current research shows that phraseology is one of the key components of language due to its high and spontaneous occurrence in daily conversation.

References

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